

Oilfield life-cycle carbon intensity estimation procedure

We calculated the life-cycle carbon intensity (CI) of oilfields in production in 2019, which included three components (upstream, midstream, and downstream). The calculation of these components relies on different data sources, input parameters, and calculators, as shown in Fig. 1.

Upstream Emissions. The calculation of upstream CI utilizes the Oil Production Greenhouse Gas Emissions Estimator (OPGEE v3.0c). The boundary considered here extends from the oil well to the refinery entrance, and encompasses greenhouse gas emissions from oilfield extraction and crude oil transportation to the refinery.

Midstream Emissions. For the midstream CI, the Oil Refinery Life-Cycle Inventory Model (PRELIM 1.6) was employed. The boundary focuses on the internal processes within the refinery, including greenhouse gas emissions from crude oil processing and refining.

Downstream Emissions. The downstream CI was calculated using the Oil Products Emissions Module (OPEM 1.1). This boundary extends from refinery exports to the end-use of oil products. Its components include greenhouse gas emissions from the transportation of oil products to end consumers and their final use.

Fig. 1. Calculation workflow for oilfield life-cycle CI, related to STAR Methods.

Upstream CI

OPGEE v3.0c is an open-source model developed by Stanford University to estimate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from crude oil extraction and transportation¹. The corresponding user guide can be found in reference². The workflow for the calculation of the upstream CI is as follows:

Step 1: collection of input parameters of OPGEE. Parameters such as oilfield production, age, and production methods were obtained primarily from Wood Mackenzie. The other parameter sources are listed in Table 1.

Step 2: Computation using the model. To capture more micro-level characteristics of the oilfields, child and standalone oilfields were selected as the calculation objects. The parameters collected from Step 1 were input into OPGEE v3.0c, and calculations were performed to obtain the upstream CI for all child and standalone oilfields. To be consistent with the research object of the global oil economic production model, we aggregated the upstream CI of child oilfields into parent oilfields in a production-weighted manner to obtain the upstream CI of parent oilfields.

Midstream CI

The midstream CI for oilfields relies on the physical characteristics of the crude oil being processed (such as sulfur content and API gravity) and the refining methods employed by refineries. To calculate the midstream CI accurately, the ideal approach is to meticulously track the paths of oil from each oilfield to its corresponding refineries. This requires detailed crude oil transportation data and refinery equipment information to determine the processing methods and energy use during processing. However, similar to previous studies, we are facing the same challenges in obtaining micro-level data at the global oil refinery level.

Inspired by Ma et al.³, we utilized the PRELIM 1.6 model to calculate the midstream CI of oilfields by maximizing its built-in crude oil type information. The midstream CI of refining the built-in crude oil type can be directly calculated using PRELIM 1.6 model, serving as the foundation for our estimation of the oilfield midstream CI. Furthermore, we assumed that the same types of crude oil undergo similar refining processes, implying convergence in their midstream CIs⁴. Therefore, we first calculated the midstream CI for all built-in crude oil types using PRELIM 1.6. We then developed a midstream CI inventory by categorizing the built-in crude oil types into different groups based on the integrated information of their resource countries and their physical characteristics (sulfur content and API gravity). Subsequently, we used the developed midstream CI inventory to obtain all the CIs of global oilfields. The following is a detailed outline of the calculation process.

Step 1: Calculate the midstream CIs for all built-in crude oil types using PRELIM 1.6. PRELIM 1.6, an open-source model developed by the University of Calgary^{5,6}, was designed to estimate the energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions associated with the refining and processing of various types of crude oil. PRELIM 1.6 encompasses a database of 684 different types of crude oils with distinct physical characteristics from various countries and oil companies. This comprehensive database effectively represents a wide array of global crude oil³. Using the processing methods^{4,7} provided by PRELIM 1.6, we calculated the midstream CI

for all built-in crude oil types.

Step 2: develop a midstream CI inventory of different crude oil types.

(1) An upper-level classification of built-in crude oil types was conducted in different countries. Because the names of most built-in crude oil types contain either the resource country or geographic location information, we can classify built-in crude oil types into different countries. Using keywords in the names of built-in crude oil types, we successfully classified 655 crude oil types to 64 different countries.

(2) Lower-level classification of built-in crude oil types was conducted for different physical characteristic groups. There are six major categories of oilfields based on their physical characteristics: heavy sweet, heavy sour, medium sweet, medium sour, light sweet, and light sour. Using a classification method outlined in the literature⁴ (details are provided in Table 2), we further classified the built-in crude oil types in each country into different physical characteristic groups. The core information used in the classification included the API gravity and sulfur content. Lastly, built-in crude oil types were categorized into different groups based on the integrated information of the country and physical characteristics.

(3) The average midstream CI for each categorized group was calculated. Based on the secondary classification results, we calculated the average midstream CI of all crude oil types within the same group (country and physical characteristics). Therefore, we obtained the average midstream CI for each categorized group in the developed inventory.

Step 3: The midstream CI of each oilfield is obtained using the developed midstream CI inventory. For every global oilfield considered in our study, country information and physical characteristic information were drawn from the Wood Mackenzie database⁸, which was used to determine its group in the developed inventory. The midstream CI of the specific global oilfield was then set as the average CI value of its determined group in the inventory. The global oilfields considered in this study belong to 93 countries, which is more than the number of countries (64) in the developed midstream CI inventory. For an oilfield that cannot be matched to the country groups in the developed inventory, its midstream CI is filled with information on the average CI values of all built-in crude oil types with the same physical characteristics group.

Downstream CI

Based on the results of the PRELIM 1.6 model in Section 3.2 and the assumption that similar crude oil types have comparable downstream CI⁹, we calculated the downstream CI for oilfields using the OPEM 1.1 model. The OPEM 1.1 model is intricately connected to the PRELIM 1.6 model, where the outputs of the latter, such as the types and proportions of petroleum products, serve as core input parameters for the former. Therefore, we first calculated the downstream CI for all built-in crude oil types in PRELIM 1.6 using OPEM 1.1. We then developed a downstream CI inventory based on the classification results of built-in crude oil types in Section 3.2. Subsequently, we used the developed downstream CI inventory to obtain all the CIs of global oilfields. The following is a detailed outline of the calculation process.

Step 1: collect input parameters of OPEM 1.1. OPEM 1.1 is an open-source model developed by the Carnegie Endowment for International Peace to assess greenhouse gas

emissions from the end use and transportation of oil products¹⁰, whose parameters are closely linked to factors such as the proportion of refined oil products, oil product transportation distances, and transportation modules. The primary inputs of OPEM include the types of oil products and their quantities and weights, which are derived from the oil product slate in PRELIM 1.6. Other parameters included transportation distances for different transportation modules from refineries to end-use locations, which were drawn from the OCI+ website⁹ with additional data from literature sources for specific countries¹¹⁻¹⁴. Additionally, it was assumed that all oil products were fully combusted when used.

Step 2: Develop a downstream CI inventory for different types of crude oil. Utilizing the input parameters obtained in Step 1, we first calculated the downstream CI for the 684 built-in crude oil types using OPEM 1.1. We then calculated the average downstream CI of all crude oil types within the same group (same country and physical characteristics) based on the categorized group results in Section 3.2. Therefore, we obtained the average downstream CI for each categorized group in the developed inventory.

Step 3: The downstream CI of each oilfield is obtained using the developed downstream CI inventory. In Step 3 of Section 3.2, we obtained the categorized group results for oilfields based on their country and physical characteristics. The downstream CI of the specific global oilfield was then set as the average CI value of its corresponding group in the inventory. Similarly, for an oilfield that cannot be matched to the country groups in the developed inventory, its downstream CI is filled with information on the average CI values of all built-in crude oil types with the same physical characteristics group.

Table 1. Sources of OPGEE Parameters, related to STAR Methods.

Parameters	Sources
Production methods, Field location, Field name, Field age, Field depth, Oil production volume, Offshore, Number of producing wells, Number of water injecting wells, Reservoir pressure, Reservoir temperature, American Petroleum Institute (API) gravity, Gas-to-oil ratio (GOR), Gas composition	Wood Mackenzie ⁸
Flaring-to-oil ratio	Masnadi et al. ¹⁵ , World Bank ¹⁶
Crude oil transport	Ankathi et al. ¹⁷ , Yang <i>et al.</i> ¹¹ , Rahman <i>et al.</i> ¹² , Patil <i>et al.</i> ¹³ , Greene et al. ¹⁸ , Nimana et al. ¹⁹
Parameters of public oilfields	Cooney et al. ²⁰ , Masnadi et al. ²¹ , Masnadi et al. ²²
Others	OPGEE default

Table 2. Classification of Crude Oil Physical Properties, related to STAR Methods.

Type	API gravity (°)	Sulfur content (wt%)	Classification
Light	>32	≤0.5	Sweet Light
		>0.5	Sour Light
Medium	22-32	≤0.5	Sweet Medium
		>0.5	Sour Medium
Heavy	≤22	≤0.5	Sweet Heavy
		>0.5	Sour Heavy

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